

ON THE FORMULATION OF THE ENERGY METHOD TO COMPUTE FLUTTER SATURATED SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The energy method is widely used for flutter stability analysis of turbomachinery due to its simplicity and low computational cost, relying on the evaluation of aerodynamic work and structural dissipation over a vibration cycle. However, in some cases, when applied to systems with nonlinear contact forces, such as those at blade roots, interlocked shrouds, or underplatform dampers, the method can underestimate frictional energy dissipation, leading to inaccurate predictions of limit cycle oscillation amplitudes. This work investigates the use of the energy method to predict the flutter-saturated response of low-pressure turbine rotors with nonlinear friction interfaces.

To assess these limitations, two structural representations are considered: a reduced-order mass-spring model and a detailed finite element model of a realistic LPT rotor. In both cases, the results are compared with reference solutions obtained from direct time-integration simulations. For configurations where the standard formulation fails, a corrected approach that accounts for nonlinear structural effects in the contact regions is proposed. This correction significantly improves agreement with reference solutions for the detailed realistic model while preserving the computational efficiency. The equations of the standard and the corrected energy methods are consistently derived using asymptotic techniques from both bladed-disk models.

INTRODUCTION

Modern bladed disks are increasingly designed closer to their mechanical limits in order to improve aerodynamic performance and reduce weight. While these design choices

enhance efficiency, they also make the components more susceptible to aeroelastic phenomena and high levels of vibration, which can lead to high-cycle fatigue (HCF) or even structural failure [1].

The two primary aeroelastic problems in turbomachinery are forced response and flutter [2, 3]. In forced response, blade vibrations are driven by external periodic excitations, typically caused by flow-field asymmetries generated by adjacent blade rows. It is a synchronous vibration in which the blades respond with the same frequency of the forcing. Flutter, in contrast, is a self-excited instability that occurs when the structure extracts energy from the surrounding flow during oscillation, which end up oscillating with the elastic modal frequency (non-synchronous vibration) and with an amplitude that grows exponentially.

Low-pressure turbine (LPT) blades are particularly prone to flutter due to their slender geometry and high aerodynamic loading [4]. Once flutter occurs, any initial blade motion grows exponentially until it is limited by dissipative mechanisms, leading to a limit cycle oscillation (LCO) [5]. In LPTs, the dominant source of dissipation often arises from friction forces at contact interfaces, such as blade roots, interlocked shrouds, and underplatform dampers, where relative motion between surfaces converts vibrational energy into heat [6, 7].

Predicting the amplitude of these LCOs is essential for estimating component life and ensuring safe operation. However, this task is challenging for two main reasons:

1. Friction and aerodynamic forces are nonlinear and relatively small compared to inertial forces, and their effects only become apparent over many vibration periods.
2. Direct coupling with the aerodynamic problem is computationally intensive, particularly for realistic blade

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geometries and operating conditions.

Fortunately, due to the typically small vibration amplitudes in turbomachinery, the aeroelastic problem in LPTs can often be studied using linearized aerodynamic models, which greatly reduce computational requirements while still capturing the essential fluid–structure interaction mechanisms [5].

Several computational strategies have been developed to estimate the flutter-saturated state:

- Direct time integration is the most straightforward approach, solving the fully coupled nonlinear equations of motion over many vibration cycles. Even with modal reduction, this method remains expensive because of the long simulation times required to resolve aerodynamic and frictional effects [8, 9].
- The Harmonic Balance Method (HBM) assumes periodic blade motion described by a finite number of Fourier harmonics. This method is significantly more efficient than direct time integration and has been successfully applied to both forced response and flutter problems [10, 11].
- The energy method offers an even more CPU-efficient alternative. Since relative motion at contact interfaces is typically small, the elastic modes computed with the contacts fully bonded (i.e., without slip) often provide a good approximation of the actual blade motion. The method estimates frictional dissipation by prescribing this elastic mode, extracting the relative displacements and contact forces, and computing the work done by friction forces over a vibration cycle [12, 13].

The validity of the energy method has been investigated in previous studies. For example, [14] analyzed an LPT rotor with nonlinear friction forces at the shroud contacts. In their work, the rotor was aerodynamically unstable and reached a bounded LCO through frictional dissipation. The LCO amplitude was computed using the energy method with several levels of coupling between the fluid and the structure. Their results showed that while the aerodynamic work could be well approximated as linear, frictional dissipation was significantly underestimated when using full stuck modes (modes without relative movement between the contact pairs), leading to incorrect LCO amplitude prediction.

The objective of the present work is to investigate flutter saturation in LPT blades due to friction forces and to evaluate the performance of the energy method in this context. Models with two different levels of detail are considered: a reduced-order mass–spring model and a detailed finite element model of a realistic blade geometry. The energy method is applied to both cases, and for configurations where the standard approach fails, a corrected version of the method is proposed. The differences between the standard and corrected formulations are highlighted, along with their implications for accurate LCO

FIGURE 1. SIMPLIFIED MASS-SPRING MODEL OF BLADED-DISK.

amplitude prediction.

FRICTION SATURATED FLUTTER SOLUTIONS

Flutter instability can be saturated by nonlinear friction forces. When this happens, the energy absorbed by the aerodynamic forces is compensated by the energy dissipated at the frictional contacts, leading to a limit cycle oscillation (LCO) solution. Typically, cantilever bladed disks with a close-to-flat unstable modal family have multiple, and not a single, unstable modes. Therefore, multiple LCO solutions exist, one for each mode close to the most unstable mode. For tuned configurations, these solutions are made primarily of a single unstable TW mode and are reached after a very slow selection process between the unstable modes [15].

All this is shown using 2 models: a simplified mass-spring model and a detailed model or a realistic bladed disk.

Reduced Mass-Spring Model

In order to illustrate the flutter behaviour, the simplified mass-spring model shown in Fig. 1 is used. In these model, each sector of the bladed-disk consists of two Degrees Of Freedom (DOFs) x and y corresponding to the blade and the fir-tree. The disk is considered to be very stiff, leading to very small elastic coupling between sectors, and is not included in the model. These DOFs are associated to the lumped masses m_b and m_f . A linear spring with stiffness k_b , representing the stiffness of the blade, connects the lumped masses. The fir-tree mass m_f is connected to a rigid platform, representing the disk, through a nonlinear microslip friction element represented by F_f . The equations of motion of a sector of the model are expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} m_b \ddot{x} + k_b(x - y) + F_a(x, \dot{x}) &= 0 \\ m_f \ddot{y} + k_b(y - x) + F_f(y) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In this paper, the only aerodynamic forces $F_a(x, \dot{x})$ that are considered are those generated by the motion of the airfoils.

FIGURE 2. AERODYNAMIC DAMPING OF MASS-SPRING ROM.

These forces are computed using the semi-uncoupled method [5] that assumes:

1. The motion of the airfoils is harmonic and the vibration frequency and the displacements of the airfoils are prescribed.
2. The amplitude of vibration is assumed to be small, allowing to linearize the unsteady aerodynamic forces.

Thanks to these assumptions, the aerodynamic forces are expressed through the aerodynamic stiffness and damping matrices, \mathbf{K}_a and \mathbf{C}_a , as:

$$\mathbf{F}_a(\mathbf{x}, \dot{\mathbf{x}}) = \mathbf{K}_a \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{C}_a \dot{\mathbf{x}} \quad (2)$$

Notice that bold is used to refer to vectors and matrices, since the aerodynamic forces couple the different sectors of the structure and \mathbf{K}_a and \mathbf{C}_a are full matrices. From these matrices, the aerodynamic characteristics, computed for the elastic frequency of the blades $\omega_0 = \sqrt{k_b/m_b}$, are shown in Fig. 2.

The friction forces $F_f(y)$ depend only on the displacement of each sector. In this work, the Oloffson microslip friction model [16] is used to compute the nonlinear forces. The expression of the friction force is:

$$F_f = F_f^* \pm 2\mu N \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{|y - y^*|}{2y_c} \right)^{5/2} \right] \quad (3)$$

This microslip model, successfully used in previous studies to model bladed disk structures, was derived to model the frictional behaviour of contacts under harmonic excitation. The superscript * refers to the values at the end of the previous loading/unloading cycle. The friction force in the limit of the microslip regime corresponds to μN , force that would be obtained for a friction displacement y_c . With these 2 parameters the equivalent stiffness of the friction contact is defined as $k_f = \mu N/y_c$.

The reduced model parameters are gathered in Table 1. With them, the model is integrated in time using a second order Runge-Kutta method. Different final solutions are obtained depending on the initial conditions. In all cases, these solutions

FIGURE 3. TIME EVOLUTION OF TW AMPLITUDES OF ROM.

m_b	k_b	m_f	k_f	μN
1	1	0.1	25	250

TABLE 1. MASS-SPRING MODEL PARAMETERS.

were made of one of the most unstable TW modes (TWs 4 to 6 according to Fig. 2). As an example, the time evolution of the modes for a case where the most unstable TW remains is shown in Fig. 3. In the figure a first regime, corresponding to the initial 200 cycles, is shown where all TWs evolve according to their aerodynamic damping and the friction effect is small. After this, the friction force becomes important enough to saturate the flutter and a slow selection process starts where all TW modes decays except from one. The decay rates of the TWs depend on the differences between aerodamping of the modes [15]. However, as shown in [8], the vibration amplitude converges after the initial 200 cycles and remains constant throughout this selection process that only involves changes in phase between blades.

Detailed model

All the features of the flutter saturated response of the previous mass-spring model are reproduced in more detailed models. To show this, the FEM model of the realistic Low Pressure Turbine (LPT) rotor of the European ARIAS project [17] is used. This rotor made of 144 blades is plotted in Fig. 4 where the mesh of a single blade is highlighted. The bladed disk is discretized with second-order tetrahedral elements using Salome [18]. The FEM matrices are generated using Calculix [19], obtaining a system with over 3.6 million DOFs.

The equations of motion of the bladed-disk, once the mass and stiffness matrices are divided into blocks corresponding to the elastic and contact DOFs, can be written as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{ee} & \mathbf{M}_{ec} \\ \mathbf{M}_{ce} & \mathbf{M}_{cc} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_e \\ \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_c \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{ee} & \mathbf{K}_{ec} \\ \mathbf{K}_{ce} & \mathbf{K}_{cc} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}_e \\ \mathbf{x}_c \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{F}_a(\mathbf{x}_e, \dot{\mathbf{x}}_e) \\ \mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{x}_c) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

FIGURE 4. FEM MODEL OF ARIAS LPT ROTOR.

where the elastic and contact DOFs correspond to \mathbf{x}_e and \mathbf{x}_c respectively. The contact forces $\mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{x}_c)$ only depend on the contact DOFs, and the aerodynamic forcing $\mathbf{F}_a(\mathbf{x}_e, \dot{\mathbf{x}}_e)$ acts only on the elastic DOFs.

To reduce the size of the problem and make its numerical solution feasible, the Craig-Bampton reduction method is applied to the system of equations 4. To express the system on these coordinates, the Craig-Bampton transformation matrix, \mathbf{T}_{CB} , is applied:

$$\mathbf{T}_{CB} = \begin{pmatrix} \Phi & \Psi \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}_e \\ \mathbf{x}_c \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{T}_{CB} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{x}_c \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{a} is a vector with the amplitudes of the full stuck modes of the complete structure retained in the reduction. The matrix Φ contains in its columns the mode shapes retained in the reduction process, these modes are normalized with respect to the mass matrix $\Phi^T \mathbf{M}_{ee} \Phi = \mathbf{I}$. And the columns of $\Psi = -\mathbf{K}_{ee}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{ec}$ are the so-called constraint modes, which are the static displacements of the elastic DOF induced by a unit displacement of each of the contact DOF. Previous equation is substituted in system 4 and the resulting equations are premultiplied by \mathbf{T}_{CB}^T getting to:

$$\left[\begin{pmatrix} \Omega^2 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{xx} \end{pmatrix} - \omega^2 \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{M}_{ax} \\ \mathbf{M}_{xa} & \mathbf{M}_{xx} \end{pmatrix} \right] \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{x}_c \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{G}_a(\mathbf{a}, \dot{\mathbf{a}}) \\ \mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{x}_c) \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The diagonal matrix Ω^2 contains all stuck frequencies squared, and the rest of the matrices are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M}_{ax} &= \mathbf{M}_{xa}^T = \Phi^T \mathbf{M}_{ee} \Psi + \Phi^T \mathbf{M}_{ec} \\ \mathbf{M}_{xx} &= \Psi^T \mathbf{M}_{ee} \Psi + \Psi^T \mathbf{M}_{ec} + \mathbf{M}_{ec} \Psi + \mathbf{M}_{cc} \\ \mathbf{K}_{xx} &= \mathbf{K}_{cc} - \Psi^T \mathbf{K}_{ee} \Psi \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

FIGURE 5. NATURAL FREQUENCIES OF 1ST FLAP AND 1ST TORSION MODAL FAMILIES OF ARIAS LPT.

The contact forces $\mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{x}_c)$ remain unchanged. And, regarding the aerodynamic forces, only their projection into the elastic modes is considered $\mathbf{G}_a(\mathbf{a}, \dot{\mathbf{a}}) = \Phi^T \mathbf{F}_a(\mathbf{x}_e, \dot{\mathbf{x}}_e)$.

The new system is expressed using a mixed formulation; the elastic modes are expressed in Fourier basis while the contact displacements are expressed in physical basis. This has the advantage that, on one hand, the elastic matrices are block diagonal and the implementation of the linearized aerodynamic coefficients is straightforward. On the other hand, the nonlinear contact forces are directly evaluated in the displacement basis, eliminating the need for intermediate transformations. See [9] for a more detailed description of the method.

The first 2 modal families, corresponding to first flap and torsion modes, are retained in the reduction. The natural frequencies of both families are shown in Fig. 5. It is observed that the differences in frequency between the modes of the same family are small due to the weak coupling between sectors.

To include the aerodynamic forces, the linearized aerodynamic coefficients of the first modal family are used. The aerodynamic damping, computed by ITP Aero using their linearized frequency domain solver Must-L [20], is presented in Fig. 6. The bladed disk is clearly unstable for a wide range of nodal diameters, being the TW_{25} the most unstable mode. The coefficients of the second family are not included because they show only marginal instability, and are expected to not have an impact on the flutter response [8].

For this study, Jenkins elements are used between the node pairs in contact $\mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{x}_c)$, where nonlinear springs are considered for the contact forces in the directions normal to the contact planes. And for the forces in the contact planes, Coulomb friction laws are considered. The expression of the normal force N is:

$$N = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } (x_n + h_n) \leq 0 \\ k_n(x_n + h_n) & \text{if } (x_n + h_n) > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

FIGURE 6. AERODYNAMIC DAMPING OF DETAILED MODEL.

where k_n is the normal contact stiffness, x_n is the displacement in the normal direction, and h_n models an initial gap between the contacts. The normal force is proportional to the penetration length in the direction perpendicular to the contact plane, and vanishes when there is separation. The tangential forces T are computed based on the contact state of the node pair (stick, slip, or separation) as:

$$T = \begin{cases} k_f(x_t - w_t) & \text{if } N > 0 \text{ and } T < \mu N \\ \mu N & \text{if } N > 0 \text{ and } k_f(x_t - w_t) \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } N \leq 0 \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

where μ is the friction coefficient, k_f is the tangential contact stiffness, x_t is the tangential relative displacement between the contact pair, and w_t is the slip displacement; if the contact is stuck, w_t remains constant and the spring is allowed to change length and, if it is slipping, w_t follows x_t .

k_n	h_n	k_f	μ
5×10^9	0	5×10^9	0.45

TABLE 2. DETAILED MODEL PARAMETERS.

The model parameters are gathered in Table 2. With respect to the contact between blades and disk, 8 contact pairs are considered on each sector (2 pairs on each contact surface). The system is integrated in time using a second order implicit Crank-Nicolson method. As in the case of the mass-spring model, different final solutions are obtained depending on the initial conditions. And, in all cases, these solutions were made of one of the most unstable TW modes (TWs 20 to 30 according to Fig. 6). As an example, the time evolution of the modes for a case where the most unstable TW remains is shown in Fig. 7. Qualitatively, the solutions is the same as that from the reduced model (Fig. 3). A first regime, corresponding to the initial 200 cycles, is shown where all TWs evolve according to

FIGURE 7. TIME EVOLUTION OF TW AMPLITUDES OF DETAILED MODEL.

their aerodynamic damping and the friction effect is small. After this, the friction force becomes important enough to saturate the flutter and a slow selection process starts where all TW modes decays except from one. Since, the differences between aerodamping is smaller for this detailed case than in the previous case, a higher number of vibration cycles is required to reach the final single mode state. Once again, the vibration amplitude converges after the initial 200 cycles and remains constant throughout this selection process that only involves changes in phase between blades.

STANDARD ENERGY METHOD

As previously mentioned, flutter saturated solutions occur when the energy dissipated by the dry friction compensates the aerodynamic work introduced by air flow. This is the foundation of the energy method, which is based on imposing the energy equilibrium equation:

$$W_{aero}(\delta_a) = W_{friction}(\delta_f) \quad (10)$$

In previous equation, δ_a stands for the blade vibration amplitude, associated with aerodynamic forces, while δ_f stands for the vibration amplitude at the fir-tree or the contact nodes, associated with friction. This is sketched in Fig. 8. To numerically solve this equilibrium, in first place, a blade vibration is imposed with different amplitudes with the shape and frequency of the mode of interest and considering full stuck contacts. The aerodynamic work can be computed for the different amplitudes of vibration. Secondly, the dissipation produced at the frictional contact due to this vibration is obtained for the different mode amplitudes. The equilibrium amplitude is the crossing between both work expressions.

FIGURE 8. SKETCH OF ENERGY METHOD (FROM [21]).

Energy method derivation

The energy method was successfully applied to computed the saturated flutter solutions of reduced mass-spring models in previous studies [22, 23]. Here, it is applied to the reduced model presented in Fig. 1, where δ_a identifies as x and δ_f as y . For simplicity, and based on the results presented in section , a single sector is considered with an aerodamping corresponding to the most unstable unstable value of Fig. 2.

The energy method can be derived from Eq. 1 using a multiple scales technique. To do this, the solution is first expanded as

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x^0(t, \tau) + x^1(t, \tau) + \dots \\ y &= y^0(t, \tau) + y^1(t, \tau) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where t is the time scale of the elastic vibration and τ is a slow time scale associated to the modulation of this elastic vibration due to friction and aerodynamic forces.

As described, firstly, the blade vibration is considered without friction displacement ($y^0 = 0$). Aerodynamic forces are neglected in this order as they are small compared to elastic forces, leading to the free vibration problem:

$$m_b \ddot{x}^0 + k_b x^0 = 0 \rightarrow x^0 = a^0(\tau) e^{i\omega_0 t} + c.c. \quad (12)$$

The blade vibrates with the natural frequency ω_0 and the amplitude of the vibration $a^0(\tau)$ is modulated in the slow time scale.

Secondly, the effect of this blade vibration on the fir-tree is considered by introducing the previous expression in the second equation of system 1 and getting to:

$$k_b y^1 - k_b a^0(\tau) e^{i\omega_0 t} + F(y^1) = 0 \rightarrow y^1(t, \tau) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} P_k(a^0, \tau) e^{ik\omega_0 t} \quad (13)$$

With the previously introduced the friction model from expression 3, this nonlinear equation is solved for different values of the blade vibration.

Finally, after considering the second term of the expansion in the first equation of system 1, the dissipation produced at the fir-tree is equilibrated with the aerodynamic forces in the amplitude equation obtained:

$$-2 \frac{\partial^2 x^0}{\partial t \partial \tau} + k_b P_1(a^0, \tau) e^{i\omega_0 t} - f_{aero} = 0 \quad (14)$$

This equation gives the dynamic evolution of the modes in the slow time scale and reproduces the mode selection process presented in previous section. In this work it is accounted directly for the final saturated state just by dropping the time derivative, leading to the expression:

$$\frac{Q(|a^0|)}{(k_f/k_b)} \cdot a^0(\tau) = k_b (2\eta_a + 2i\xi_a) \cdot a^0(\tau) \quad (15)$$

Where, for simplicity, the friction term is split as $P_1(a^0, \tau) = Q(|a^0|)/k_f \cdot a^0(\tau)$ where the real and imaginary parts of the function Q represent the friction damping and friction stiffness normalized with the friction stiffness respectively. And the aerodynamic force was expressed using the linearized coefficients as $f_{aero} = k_b (2\eta_a + 2i\xi_a) \cdot a^0(\tau)$. Notice that the force equilibrium equation 15 is totally equivalent to the energy equilibrium equation 10 and can be recovered just by multiplying both size by the conjugate of the vibration amplitude $\overline{a^0}(\tau)$.

Application to Mass-spring model

If the energy method is applied to the mass-spring model, the friction function Q related to the Olofsson microslip model is obtained and presented in Fig. 9. According to equation 15, the amplitude of vibration $|a^0|$ is obtained from the equilibrium of the aerodamping and the imaginary part of Q , as sketched in Fig. 9.

The amplitude of vibration obtained with the energy method is plotted together with the results from the time integration in Fig. 3. The value is plotted as a constant horizontal line as the saturated amplitude was targeted from the beginning. The matching between the final vibration amplitudes of both methods is very good, with a relative error of 4.3% that is in the order of the small parameter used in the multiple scales technique k_b/k_f . The friction cycles obtained with both methods present a very good matching as well, as shown in Fig. 10, confirming the capability of the method to account for the interaction of flutter and nonlinear friction in mass-spring models.

FIGURE 9. FRICTION DAMPING AND FREQUENCY CORRECTION PARAMETERS.

FIGURE 10. FRICTION CYCLES OF ROM MODEL. COMPARISON OF TIME INTEGRATIO AND ENERGY METHOD.

Application to Detailed model

The energy method is applied now to the detailed model of the ARIAS LPT rotor shown in Fig. 4.

On this method, and according to previous time integration results, the structure is assumed to vibrate following a single elastic mode:

$$\mathbf{M}_{ee}\ddot{\mathbf{x}}_e^0 + \mathbf{K}_{ee}\mathbf{x}_e^0 = \mathbf{0} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}_e^0 = \phi \cdot a^0(\tau)e^{i\omega_0\tau} + c.c. \quad (16)$$

Where ϕ corresponds to the mode of vibration, in this case the most unstable mode of the modal family. And a^0 and ω_0 are the amplitude and frequency of vibration of ϕ respectively.

Subsequently, the effect of this vibration on the friction contacts is evaluated, getting to equation:

$$\mathbf{K}_{ce}\mathbf{x}_c^1 + \mathbf{K}_{ce}\mathbf{x}_e^0 = \mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{x}_c^1) \rightarrow \mathbf{x}_c^1 = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_k(a, \tau)e^{ik\omega_0\tau} \quad (17)$$

From this equilibrium, the friction function Q presented in dashed lines in Fig. 11 is obtained. As shown from the figure, the effect of friction forces obtained with this method is very small and, when trying to solve the energy equilibrium equation 14, no solution is found. The friction dissipation is not high enough to compensate the aerodynamic work regardless of the vibration amplitude $|a^0|$. The maximum flutter instability that the friction could saturate according to this method corresponded to $\xi_{aero} = -5 \times 10^{-7}$ what is in clear contradiction to the time integration and the experimental results presented in [17]. These results point out the clear underprediction of friction obtained when the standard energy method is applied to a realistic structure.

CORRECTED ENERGY METHOD

Based on the previous results, the energy method was revised. On this section, the revised version of the energy method, called here corrected energy method, is presented in first place. The method derived is later applied to the realistic ARIAS LPT model to test it.

Corrected energy method derivation

To derive a corrected energy method, capable of accounting for the real friction effects on realistic bladed disk geometries, the system of equations of the model is expressed in the Craig-Bampton basis. To do this, the Craig-Bampton change of basis matrix 5 getting to the system of equations 6. At this point, all the elastic modes of the system are included and no reduction is applied to the system yet.

To derive the equilibrium equation, the same multiple scales technique is applied to the new system of equations, where the variables are expanded as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a} &= \mathbf{a}^0(t, \tau) + \mathbf{a}^1(t, \tau) + \dots \\ \mathbf{x}_c &= \mathbf{x}_c^0(t, \tau) + \mathbf{x}_c^1(t, \tau) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

As in the standard energy method, first, the elastic blade vibration is solved with no contact displacements ($\mathbf{x}_c^0 = \mathbf{0}$) and a single mode:

$$(\Omega^2 - \omega^2\mathbf{I})\mathbf{a}^0 = 0 \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^0(t, \tau) = (1, 0, \dots, 0)^T \cdot a(\tau)e^{i\omega_0\tau} \quad (19)$$

In this case, the first full stuck mode is considered but the same method could be applied for any different mode. Subsequently, the effect of the mode vibration on the frictional contacts is evaluated solving the second block of equations as:

$$\mathbf{K}_{xx}\mathbf{x}_c^1 - \omega_0^2\mathbf{M}_{xa}\mathbf{a}^0 = \mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{x}_c^1) \rightarrow \mathbf{x}_c^1 = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_k(a, \tau)e^{ik\omega_0\tau} \quad (20)$$

This nonlinear system of equations can be solved getting to an expression of the contact displacements for different values of the vibration amplitude $\mathbf{a}^0(t, \tau)$.

In third place, the energy equilibrium is obtained after applying the solvability condition of the second order expansion term of the elastic displacements equations $\mathbf{a}^1(t, \tau)$. The equation takes the form:

$$-2 \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{a}^0}{\partial t \partial \tau} + \omega_0^2 \mathbf{M}_{ax} \mathbf{P}_1(a, \tau) e^{i\omega_0 t} - \mathbf{G}_a(\mathbf{a}, \dot{\mathbf{a}}) = 0 \quad (21)$$

That can be projected into the mode of interest premultiplying by $(1, 0, \dots, 0)^T$. The aerodynamic forces can be expressed by mean of the linearized aerodynamic coefficients. If only the final equilibrium equation is of interest, it is obtained:

$$\omega_0^2 Q(|a|) \cdot a(\tau) = \omega_0^2 (2\eta_a + 2i\xi_a) \cdot a(\tau) \quad (22)$$

Where once again the friction function has been expressed as a complex damping and frequency correction $(1, 0, \dots, 0)^T \mathbf{M}_{ax} \mathbf{P}_1(a, \tau) = Q(|a|) \cdot \mathbf{a}^0(\tau)$.

Notice that the only difference between the standard and the corrected method appears on the nonlinear equations where the blade vibration and the friction forces are compensated (equations 13 and 20 respectively). If the effect of the blade motion on the contact equations is identified with $-\omega_0^2 \mathbf{M}_{xa} \mathbf{a}^0$ in the corrected equation, the only difference between the methods corresponds to the elastic term, that recalling its definition is:

$$\mathbf{K}_{xx} = \mathbf{K}_{cc} - \Psi^T \mathbf{K}_{ce} \Psi = \mathbf{K}_{cc} - \mathbf{K}_{ce} \mathbf{K}_{ee}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{ec} \quad (23)$$

The term takes into account the effect in the contacts of the motion of themselves through the coupling to the elastic DOF. This induces larger displacements and this contribution is crucial to obtain an accurate estimation of the friction effects.

Corrected energy method results

The described corrected method is applied to the detailed ARIAS LPT rotor of Fig. 4. The friction function Q shown in Fig. 11 in solid lines is obtained by considering that the vibration happens with the most unstable TW mode of the first modal family (corresponding to the critical case [8]). It is clear when compared with the results from the standard energy method the change on the friction effects. In this particular case, there is a difference of 4 orders of magnitude between both methods.

Looking at the shape of the damping curve, this can be split in 5 intervals. It is possible to see corners in the points where 2 intervals join. The first interval spans from zero amplitude to $|a^0| \approx 0.25$ and corresponds to the regime where all contacts are in stick and there is no friction dissipation. In each of the other 4 intervals one contact pair starts to slide and dissipate energy. In the last interval, from $|a^0| \approx 0.45$ on, all the 4 contacts of the

FIGURE 11. FRICTION DAMPING AND FREQUENCY CORRECTION PARAMETERS FOR DETAILED MODEL OBTAINED WITH STANDARD AND CORRECTED ENERGY METHODS.

upper contact faces of the fir-tree are sliding (no activation of the friction was found for the lower contact faces of the fir-tree).

Taking ξ_{aero} from Fig. 6, the equilibrium between friction and aerodynamic forces is solved as plotted in Fig. 11. There is a very good agreement between the amplitude of vibration obtained from the corrected energy method and from the time integration as shown in Fig. 7. Actually, the error between both prediction is about 0.1% which is on the order of the small parameter used in the multiple scales technique ω_0^2/k_f .

The friction cycles obtained with both methods present a very good matching as well, as shown in Fig. 12, confirming the capability of the method to account for the interaction of flutter and nonlinear friction in detailed models. As expected looking at the damping curve, one contact pair is in stick and producing no dissipation.

In this case, this equilibrium between friction and aerodynamic forces is only fulfilled for a single $|a^0|$ (at least for the range of $|a^0|$ of Fig. 11). For more unstable cases, the equilibrium could be fulfilled for 2 different $|a^0|$, the first corresponding to a value on the left of the maximum friction dissipation, and a second on the right. Looking at the slope of the friction damping curve, it can be said that the first equilibrium would be stable, since the friction dissipation grows/decays faster than the aerodynamic when $|a^0|$ grows/decays. On the contrary, and using the same argument, the second equilibrium point would be unstable. This was validated with time integration results. This is linked with the idea that microslip friction, when not all the contact surface is sliding, is able to saturate flutter while macrosip friction is unable.

FIGURE 12. FRICTION CYCLES COMPUTED WITH TIME INTEGRATION AND CORRECTED ENERGY METHOD.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the flutter saturation of a Low-Pressure Turbine rotor has been investigated using the energy method, with emphasis on cases where nonlinear friction forces are present at contact interfaces. The derivation of the energy method, for both the standard and corrected approaches, has been presented in detail using an asymptotic technique.

The study has shown that the standard energy method can predict limit cycle oscillation (LCO) amplitudes with good accuracy for reduced mass-spring models, even in the presence of frictional interfaces. However, when applied to detailed finite element models using linear full-stick modes, the method significantly underestimates frictional energy dissipation, leading to an overprediction of LCO amplitudes.

This limitation is traced to the incomplete representation of contact motion in the frictional work calculation. Correcting the full-stick modes solely with the forces generated at the contacts is insufficient; it is also necessary to account for the forces induced by the relative motion of the contact surfaces through

their coupling with the elastic degrees of freedom. A corrected version of the energy method has been proposed that incorporates these effects while maintaining the low computational cost that makes the approach attractive for design applications.

The corrected formulation has been validated against direct time-domain simulations for both reduced-order and detailed finite element models. In all cases, the predictions closely matched the reference results, while requiring computational times several orders of magnitude lower. This makes the corrected energy method a practical and accurate tool for the design and analysis of turbomachinery components subject to flutter with nonlinear friction interfaces, combining physical fidelity with computational efficiency.

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